

Ethno-Religious Sentiments And National Integration In Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper discusses ethno-religious sentiments and national integration in Nigeria. Today, Nigeria is characterized by deep cleavages along ethnic, religious and political lines. Political and ethnic imbalances exist among and between the various states or ethnic groups that make up Nigeria. These imbalances arose from the nature and character of the post colonial Nigeria State. Thus, the decision which was made by Nigerians prior to independence to become a Republic from Britain required that Nigerians will be integrated with one another for the purpose of peaceful coexistence, co-sharing of resources, co-administering and co-development of the nation. But this aim seems to be elusive since independence. What seems to linger so much is the crises of marginalization, promotion of personal and ethnic interests such as ethnic resource control; propagation of exclusive religious ideologies and the practice of sectional and tribal politics as can be seen in Nigeria today. Lack of adequate representation by the federating states in Nigeria constitutes the greatest threat to national integration and economic development. Hence, in view of the recent events encumbering the country, the need arose for academic perusal on the issue in order to suggest a sustainable solution, so as to checkmate the national disintegration that may be triggered through ethno-religious insurgence. Data for this work were aided through the application of primary and secondary methods of data collection. The findings revealed that inasmuch as ethno-religious sentiments fan the embers of disintegration it is also a veritable tool for national integration in Nigeria if properly harnessed. This research also recommends ethno-religious tolerance and peaceful coexistence amongst Nigerians.

Keywords: Ethnicity, Religion and National Integration

Introduction

It has been variously addressed by sociological, historical, anthropological and political science scholars that the entity called Nigeria is a contraption of the British that came into being in 1914. Nigeria was put together as one nation by the British at the beginning of the 20th century when Frederick Lugard, a British colonial

administrator and the colonial office in London amalgamated the then Northern and Southern protectorates of Nigeria in the year 1914. Prior to this date, Nigeria was not a single country. It was a collection of kingdoms and tribes, some with quite sophisticated cultures. These various ethnic and cultural groups that make up what is Nigeria today existed as autonomous political

entities, having their own political system and religious values before British eventually brought them under one colonial authority with administrative areas that corresponded to major tribal divisions.

Okeke (2010) observes that “ethnicity in Nigeria derives from the multifarious and diverse nature of the Nigerian territory which consists of people of different background, ancestry and tradition” (p. 249). Member of an ethnic group could then be described as consisting of those who regard themselves as being alike by virtue of their common ancestry language, custom as well as tradition. Thus, there are the major ethnic nationalities:- Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba and the minorities like the Tiv, Ibibio, Gbagyi, and many others. In fact, Nigeria is said to be made up of about 250 distinct ethnic groups. While the Hausas occupied the extensive area in the North, the Yorubas and the Bini are in the West, the Igbos in the South with the Jukun, Igala and Nupe in the middle belt. These represent some of the many ethnic nationalities brought together by the British. However, despite the differences in ethnicity and religion, these people had the freedom to interact with each other due mainly because of the geographical nature of the country.

Agbodike (1999) further asserts that, “Nigeria is a conglomerate nation-state consisting of a multiplicity of ethnic nationalities which are heterogeneous and pluralistic in various

respects” (p. 113). It has been observed that the diversities among the various ethnic groups are best demonstrated in their differing linguistic and cultural heritage, social disparities, disproportionate population sizes, uneven economic resources, educational imbalance, historical evolution, administrative systems and religion. These diversities have tended to generate tension, mutual suspicion and distrust, intolerance and conflicts among Nigerians which have, at times, threatened and endangered the corporate existence of the country. The pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial history of Nigeria is replete with these conflicts and upheavals which have given rise on several occasions to insecurity of lives and property. Worthy of particular mention here is the history and memories of pre-colonial wars, raids, and other hostilities which were common place among the various peoples of Nigeria.

Hitherto, since independence and even before, Anyanwu (1999) observed that, “mutual ethnic distrust and suspicion have been part of the bane of the Nigerian society” (p. 23). Ethnicity and religion was at the root of the Nigerian civil war. Since the end of the war, ethno-religious competition has not been abated and Nigerian leaders have not helped in these matters. Rather, when it suits their selfish interests, they play on ethnic and religious sentiments to achieve popularity and acceptance.

An Overview of the Problems of Ethnicity and Religious Sentiments in Nigeria

The problem of acrimonious existence among the diverse groups and interests in the federation of Nigeria leading to mutual distrust and inter-community conflicts has become perennial and endemic in the nation's body-politic and has militated against the political stability of the country since independence. Also, according to Agbodike (2004) "the fear of domination of one ethnic group or section of the country by another and the national question of who gets what and how the 'national cake' should be shared constitute a major factor of this problem" (p. 177). This situation seriously hampers efforts at national integration as it applies to the building of a nation-state out of the disparate ethnic, geographic, social, economic and religious elements in the country.

Howbeit, the problems associated with Nigeria's development in the course of history are really complex. The problems are socio-economic and deep-rooted because of apparent inability and refusal of the members of the ethnic societies that compose the country to distinguish their collective needs from their greed and the most objective way to approach these needs.

Beyond the scenario and rationalization, ethnic and religious sensitivity, more importantly since the independence of Nigeria, have continued to threaten the continued co-existence, peace and

unity of Nigerians as members of one sovereign democratic state. Be that as it may, religion in all societies is said to provide a healthy terrain for a functional and vibrant society. It is regarded as the opiate of the masses and serves cohesive and euphoric functions in society. Oddly enough, the case of Nigeria is somehow different. Hence, religion according to Anugwom and Oji (2004):

functions as a means for the perpetration of violence, fueling ethnic consciousness and solidarity, acquisition of political power and socio-economic gains, massive killings and the wanton destruction and vandalization of property of those considered infidels or who pay allegiance to other religious. (p. 145).

As a means of commandeering political legitimacy in Nigeria, it has dictated the pace of the political democratization process which hitherto nurtured ethnic consciousness in the country.

Against this background, Nnoli (cited by Anugwom and Oji, 2004) stated that there has been:

an asymmetric on an opposing relationship between the two dominant religions-Islam and Christianity, in the socio-political affairs of the country. Without any doubt ethnicity arises when

social relations are antithetical to group functioning and when social groups are competitive rather than co-operative. They are characterized by cultural prejudices, varying degrees of socio-economic backwardness and political discrimination. These features are further reduced to a feeling of pride in intra-group solidarity, common consciousness and identity of the group and the exclusiveness of its members. (p. 145).

This, typically exemplifies the Nigerian situation since independence. The acrimony in the struggle for power and supremacy in the control of the state apparatus between the Christians and the moslems had often resulted in bitter fend and wanton destruction of lives and properties in Nigeria.

Thus, religion which has been proved to unite people together has also thrown this country to series of conflicts which have both religious and ethnic undertone. Ethnic and religious conflicts are inseparable in Nigeria. This is because Muslims for instance have no distinction between religious and ethnic conflicts. Ethnic conflicts for them always metamorphose into religious conflicts. Best (2001) observed that “Islam stresses the primacy of religion above other forms of identity” (p. 66). And that is why most of ethno-religious conflicts experienced in this country are mostly from Muslims

dominated areas. Udoidem (cited by Ibezim, 2014) also said that:

Islamic philosophy divides the world into two camps ‘believers’ and ‘infidels’. Believers are the moslem faithful who believe that there is only one God with Mohammed as his only true prophet. Infidels, on the other hand, consist of non-muslims, particularly Christians, who are regarded as blasphemers’ because of their belief that Jesus Christ is the son of God. (p. 94).

Christians on the other hand believe that it is only through Jesus Christ that one can go to heaven. For Udoidem, it seems that Christians and Muslims have contradictory beliefs and religious practices which tend to fuel the embers of conflicts. That is why most of the ethno-religious conflicts experienced in this country are between Christians and Muslims.

Hitherto, ethnic and religious crises have a very long history in Nigeria. The nature and dimensions of these crises take different forms and pattern of occurrence. The manifestations of these crises have often been violent and threatening to the corporate existence of Nigeria as a nation state. The conditions created have also hampered the healthy transformation and progress of Nigeria in many ways. It has led to the stagnation of the country’s development at all fronts. Following the trends of occurrence and perpetration, it may be strongly believed

that the situation has serious social, economic, political and psychological consequences pathological to the existence of the country as a functional democratic state. The scenario created by the rapid rate of ethno-religious upheavals in Nigeria today seem to question the rational for the continued co-existence of the diverse ethnic nationalities that make up the country. Anugwom and Oji (2004) adds that:

to the extent this is true, there is perhaps a rethinking in some quarters about the continued relevance of the 'Nigerianization' slogan, "unity in diversity" the patriotic citizens of this country still work hard to uphold. Due to the long spell of ethnic and religious violence in Nigeria today, the average Nigerian Christian cannot trust his Muslim counterpart in the scheme of things in this country. (p. 161).

The Christian-Igbo or Yoruba are also suspicious of the Hausa/Fulani Muslims in their relationship with one another. There can be no meaningful and functional interaction among these ethno-religious groups because there is this feeling of insecurity amongst them that make constructive relationship impossible. The Muslims for instance cannot compromise their religion and power seeking nature for any thing else in this country.

Apparently, the persistence of ethno-religious crisis in the country can be partially blamed on

the nature of the national leadership. In this sense, the leaders have fanned the embers of disunity and profited from the divisive tendencies of the various groups. Moreover, the failure of these leaders to pilot the affairs of the nation well easily makes a relapse into primordial solidarity attractive. They are ethnocentric and insensitive to the conditions of the poor who die in their numbers by being butchered in Nigerian states and streets as a result of ethnic and religious confrontations in the country. Typical example are the activities of the Boko Haram insurgency which has resulted in countless loss of lives and wanton destruction of properties and the ruthless Fulani Herdsmen killings across the country, with the latest massacre in Kaduna state. All these happening under the nose of the government that vowed to put an end to insurgence and safeguard lives and properties. While the poor souls are busy killing themselves in inter-religious and ethnic crises, the leaders are busy perpetrating corruption, fanning the embers of ethnicity and sabotaging the economy. Such leaders in defence, confuse the entire world that everything is under control. In this circumstance, the stagnation and regression of the economy and overall development of the country becomes inevitable.

This non-challant attitude of leaders in resolving the issue inspite of the constitutional guarantee of the individuals right to life, religion, freedom of movement speech and association portends

an unhealthy scenario where the country is gradually degenerating into a state of chaos, anarchy and eventual demise as a sovereign state. Above all, the image of the country is both internally and internationally denied. Many individuals and groups in the country today have become distressed economically and socially as a result of ethnic and religious conflicts characterizing the state of Nigeria. Groups and people in their thousands feel marginalized and excluded from the so-called dividends of democracy. The political environment has remained shaky and unstable since the most potent and manipulative cause of these crises no doubt is politics.

Quest for National Integration in Nigeria

National integration entails expressions in acts and willingness to belong, in every sense of that word, to a nation. Okunna (2012) stated that Shona Khurana writing about national integration in India defines national integration as the awareness of a common identity among the citizens of a country. It means that though we belong to different castes, religious and regions and speak different languages, we recognize that fact, that we are all one. This type of integration is very important in the building of a strong and prosperous nation. Also, Nnonyelu (2001) asserts that as a concept, “national integration is determined by the degree to which members and groups in a plural society adapt to the demands of national

existence while co-existing harmoniously” (p. 147). On a practical note, national integration is a process, not an end in itself and is usually affected by contending social forces. In the quest for national integration, citizens are expected to respect the overriding supremacy of the national government. This entails subordination of institutions and cultural values to the demands of the central authority with obvious sacrifices. Often, intra and inter-ethnic crisis result but the ability of the state to resolve or regulate the recurring crisis to create an enabling environment where the peoples respect and love for their nation is enhanced will affect the tempo of national integration.

Nonetheless, integration basically presupposes diversity. The reality of diversity equally entails the reality of conflict and harmony founded on the very nature of being. Nature negates monotony but thrives in diversity. The diversity of being is ontologically rooted in a fundamental unity. Thus, the beauty of nature lies in the culture of unity in diversity. While considering diversity as nature’s culture, Amaku (cited by Nweke, 2014):

avers that the beauty of the universe, according to Thomas Aquinas, consists in its manifesting ontological diversity and hierarchical structure. This unity in diversity that marks the ontology and excellence of being we can rightly describe as ‘nature’s culture’ – ‘a mode

of being'. Even nature has its 'culture'; it has the custom of substantializing itself in diversity, in multiplicity, and in unity. If diversity is inbuilt in nature, nature's habit of self-revelation, it cannot be bad; it must be depicting the mode in which nature ontologically flourishes (p. 86).

In human society, diversity is categorized into gender, races, tribes, lineages, kits and kin. The peopling of any given society is anchored on either homogeneity or heterogeneity of these categories and grounds the formation of nation-states. Integration would normally pose no problem for homogenous nations, since their statehood remain a political Institution of people with common origin (most homogeneous are Japan and Korea). Hence, their nationalism is guided by a sense of common purpose, a 'we feeling', although not negating the possibilities of intra-ethnic conflicts. The greater challenges of national integration are to be found in heterogeneous nations. In other words, nations of ethnic diversity or multi-ethnicity are often plunged into conflict of interests. Successes in addressing the challenges depend hugely and essentially on the level of political maturity evident in any such nation. For instance United States of America is an ethnic diverse nation, with lesser problems of integration consequent upon its political stature which ensures both socio-political and economic security of her

citizenry. Thus, every ethnic group in US desires to belong.

Therefore, if Nigeria can borrow a leaf from the success story of America's national integration and harness it properly, then our ethno-religious problem is half solved.

Recommended Practical Steps towards actualizing National Integration in Nigeria

- Nigerian history, culture and religion be made compulsory at all levels of education with much emphasis on those factors capable of promoting national integration - If students are taught from the cradle about their history and how they became a nation with other tribes; the pain they bore together, the success they celebrated together; the unifying values in their culture and the beauty of their diverse religious beliefs, it would instill in them a sense of unity, oneness and brotherliness thereby inhibiting the unnecessary outrage of hate and ethno-religious intolerance.
- Ethno-religious tolerance should be preached and practiced for peaceful coexistence amongst Nigerians – Parents leaders should not only preach about peaceful coexistence with fellow Nigerians but should also lead by example through their practical dispositions towards coexisting

peacefully with fellow Nigerians of ethno-religious affiliation.

- Proper and adequate representation by federating states in national matters and affairs – Political leaders should endeavour to adopt the principle of federal character in national matters so as not to favour one or more federating states to the detriment or marginalization of another as been experienced in the government of the day.
- Inter-ethnic and inter-religious marriages should be encouraged and promoted - These type of union should be greatly encouraged and promoted because it will limit mutual distrust and ethno-religious biases. Marriage is one of the most potent unifying force and as such promotes enculturation and religious tolerance which leads to national integration.
- Religious and traditional leaders should be selfless, sensitive and diplomatic in their roles for national integration.

Conclusion

There is evidence in Nigerian history to show that there are more factors making for Nigerian unity than those making for disunity. Various ethnic groups in Nigeria, prior to the colonial imposition shared some common values and historical experience which can form the foundation of national integration. Thus, the use

of ethnicity, religion and politics should rather unite us as Nigerians in order to promote peace and foster unity and harmonious peaceful co-existence. In spite of the widespread of ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria and their long history, the Nigerian governments have failed to thoroughly tackle this problem through articulate policy actions, instead, the government continues to rely on coercive method that has so far yielded little or no results.

Our experience in this research has so far revealed that ethno-religious conflicts are inevitable in a multi-ethnic and multi-religious society like Nigeria. However, it is envisaged that the full acceptance and implementation of the recommendation aforementioned would contribute immensely towards achieving national integration.

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